

ELLIPS KO'NDALANG KESIMLI TO'LDIRUVCHILI SILINDRIK QOBIQDA XOS TO'LQINNING TARQALISHI

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Annotasiya: Bu maqolada to'ldiruvchili cheksiz uzun ellips ko'ndalang kesimli silindrik qobiqda xos to'lqin tarqalishi masalasini ko'ramiz. Bunday masalalar juda kam o'rganilgan bo'lib asosan hosil bo'ladigan muvozanat yoki harakat tenglamalari murakkab xususiy hosilali integro-differensial tenglamaga keladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Ellips, qovushqoq-elastik, deformatsiya, ko'chish, kuchlanish, Lamé tenglamasi.

Аннотация: В данной статье мы рассмотрим задачу распространения волн в цилиндрической оболочке бесконечно длинного эллиптического сечения с дополнением. Подобные проблемы изучены очень мало, и полученные уравнения равновесия или движения в основном представляют собой интегро-дифференциальные уравнения со сложными частными производными.

Ключевые слова: Эллипс, вязкоупругий, деформация, смещение, напряжение, уравнение Ламе.

Abstract: In this article we will consider the problem of wave propagation in a cylindrical shell of infinitely long elliptical cross-section with complement. Similar problems have been studied very little, and the resulting equations of equilibrium or motion are mainly integro-differential equations with complex partial derivatives.

Keywords: Ellipse, viscoelastic, deformation, displacement, stress, Lamé equation.

Kirish.

Elastik muhitda joylashgan elliptik jismning xos tebranishi to'liq o'rganilmagan. Muhitning eliptik silindrik qobiqqa bo'lgan ta'siri Vinkler asosi yordamida hisobga olinadi. Eliptik qobiqning xarakat differensial tenglamasi qovushqoqlik nazariyasining Lamé tenglamasini qanoatlantiradi.

(qarang, [1],[2],[4],[5],[6],[7]).

Masalaning qo'yilishi.

Faraz qilaylik qovushqoqlik xususiyatiga ega bo'lgan cheksiz uzun ellips ko'ndalang kesimli (elliptik) silindrik jism berilgan bo'lsin. Shu jismda erkin yoki xos to'lqinlarni tarqalishini ko'ramiz.

Ko'chish, deformatsiya vektorlari va siljish potentsiallari elliptik koordinatalar sistemasida quyidagicha ifodalanadi:

$$\nabla^2 = \left[\frac{1}{J^2} \left(\frac{\partial^2}{\partial \xi^2} + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \eta^2} \right) + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial z^2} \right], J = \frac{c}{2} (ch2\xi - \cos 2\eta)$$

Agar φ_j bo'ylama to'lqin o'rganilsa s_{0j} olinadi, ψ_j ko'ndalang to'lqin o'rganilsa s_{0sj} olinadi. Vektor ko'rinishdagi ifodani ko'chish komponentalari orqali quyidagicha yozish mumkin.

$$u_\xi = \frac{1}{J} \left(\frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial \xi} + \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \eta} + l \frac{\partial \chi}{\partial z} \right), u_\eta = \frac{1}{J} \left(\frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial \eta} - \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \xi} + l \frac{\partial \chi}{\partial z} \right), u_z = \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial z} + l \left(\frac{\partial^2}{\partial z^2} - \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} \right) \chi. \quad (3.1)$$

Xuddi shunday deformatsiya komponentlarini ham ko'chish komponentlari orqali elliptik tipdagi koordinatalarda ifodalash mumkin

$$\varepsilon_{\xi\xi} = \frac{1}{aJ} \left(\frac{\partial u_\xi}{\partial \xi} + \frac{\sin 2\eta}{2J^2} u_\eta \right), \varepsilon_{\eta\eta} = \frac{1}{aJ} \left(\frac{\partial u_\eta}{\partial \eta} + \frac{s h 2\xi}{2J^2} u_\xi \right), \varepsilon_{zz} = \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial z},$$

$$\varepsilon_{\xi\eta} = \frac{1}{2aJ^3} \left[J^2 \left(\frac{\partial u_\xi}{\partial \eta} + \frac{\partial u_\eta}{\partial \xi} \right) - \frac{\sin 2\eta}{2} u_\xi - \frac{s h 2\xi}{2} u_\eta \right], \quad (3.2)$$

$$\varepsilon_{\xi z} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial u_{\xi}}{\partial z} + \frac{1}{aJ} \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial \xi} \right), \varepsilon_{\eta z} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial u_{\eta}}{\partial z} + \frac{1}{aJ} \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial \eta} \right).$$

Umumlashgan Guk qonunidan operator kuchlanishlarni ham ko'chishlar yoki deformatsiya orqali ifodalash mumkin

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{\xi\xi} &= \frac{(\bar{\lambda} + 2\bar{\mu})}{aJ} \frac{\partial u_{\xi}}{\partial \xi} + \frac{\bar{\lambda}}{aJ} \frac{\partial u_{\eta}}{\partial \eta} + \frac{\bar{\lambda} sh 2\xi}{2aJ^3} u_{\xi} + \frac{(\bar{\lambda} + 2\bar{\mu}) \sin 2\eta}{aJ^3} u_{\eta}, \\ \sigma_{\eta\eta} &= \frac{(\bar{\lambda} + 2\bar{\mu})}{aJ} \frac{\partial u_{\eta}}{\partial \eta} + \frac{\bar{\lambda}}{aJ} \frac{\partial u_{\xi}}{\partial \xi} + \frac{\bar{\lambda}}{aJ} \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial z} + \frac{\bar{\lambda} \sin 2\eta}{2aJ^3} u_{\eta} + \frac{(\bar{\lambda} + 2\bar{\mu}) sh 2\xi}{2aJ^3} u_{\xi}, \end{aligned} \quad (3.3)$$

Elliptik koordinatalar sistemasidan qutb koordinatalar sistemasiga o'tish uchun quyidagi munosabatdan foydalanamiz.

$$r = a(ch^2 \xi - \sin^2 \eta)^{1/2}, \theta = \frac{1}{tg(th \xi tg \eta)}.$$

Masalaning yechilishi.

Ukrainalik olimlar Grinchenko V.T. va Guz A.N. ko'chish vektorini quyidagicha tasvirlashadi, $\underline{u}_1 = \text{grad} \phi + \text{rot} \psi$, bu yerda $\psi(\psi_r, \psi_{\theta}, \psi_z)$ uchta komponentga bogliq bo'ladi. Bo'ylama va ko'ndalang to'lqin potentsiallari qo'yidagicha to'lqin tenglamasini va bir-biriga bog'liq bo'lgan xususiy hosilali differensial tenglamani qanoatlantiradi

$$\nabla^2 \phi - \frac{1}{\bar{c}_p^2} \frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial t^2} = 0; \quad \nabla^2 \psi_z - \frac{1}{\bar{c}_s^2} \frac{\partial^2 \psi_z}{\partial t^2} = 0; \quad (3.4)$$

$$\nabla^2 \psi_{\theta} - \frac{\psi_{\theta}}{r^2} + \frac{2}{r^2} \frac{\partial \psi_r}{\partial \theta} - \frac{1}{\bar{c}_s^2} \frac{\partial^2 \psi_{\theta}}{\partial t^2} = 0; \quad \nabla^2 \psi_r - \frac{\psi_r}{r^2} - \frac{2}{r^2} \frac{\partial \psi_{\theta}}{\partial \theta} - \frac{1}{\bar{c}_s^2} \frac{\partial^2 \psi_r}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

$$\nabla^2 = \frac{1}{a^2 J} \left(\frac{\partial^2}{\partial \xi^2} + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \eta^2} \right) = \frac{1}{\bar{c}_s^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} - \frac{\partial^2}{\partial z^2}.$$

bu yerda $\bar{c}_s^2 = \bar{c}_x^2$; $\bar{c}_p^2 = \bar{c}_p^2$;

Oxirgi ikkita tenglamani qo'shib ayirish bilan to'lqin tenglamasiga olib kelish mumkin. Bu yerda uzun elliptik silindrning differensial tenglamalarining yechimini quyidagi ko'rinishda izlaymiz:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \varphi_k(\xi, \eta, z, t) &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \Phi_n(\xi, \eta) e^{\pm i \gamma_{pk} z} e^{-i \omega t}; \\ \psi_{rk}(\xi, \eta, z, t) &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \Psi_{nr}(\xi, \eta) e^{\pm i \gamma_{pk} z} e^{-i \omega t}; \\ \psi_{\theta k}(\xi, \eta, z, t) &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \Psi_{n\theta}(\xi, \eta) e^{\pm i \gamma_{pk} z} e^{-i \omega t}; \\ \psi_{zk}(\xi, \eta, z, t) &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \Psi_{nz}(\xi, \eta) e^{\pm i \gamma_{pk} z} e^{-i \omega t}; \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (3.5)$$

bu yerda n - butun son; γ_{pk} - to'lqin tarqalshining doimiy soni;

ω - kompleks xususiy chastota.

Agar (3.5) yechimni (3.4)ga qo'ysak qo'yidagicha tenglama hosil bo'ladi:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \frac{\partial^2 \Phi_j}{\partial \xi^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \Phi_j}{\partial \eta^2} + k_{1j}^2 (ch^2 \xi - \cos^2 \eta) \Phi_j &= 0; \\ \frac{\partial^2 \Psi_{rj}}{\partial \xi^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \Psi_{rj}}{\partial \eta^2} + k_{2j}^2 (ch^2 \xi - \cos^2 \eta) \Psi_{rj} &= 0, \\ \frac{\partial^2 \Psi_{\theta j}}{\partial \xi^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \Psi_{\theta j}}{\partial \eta^2} + k_{2j}^2 (ch^2 \xi - \cos^2 \eta) \Psi_{\theta j} &= 0, \\ \frac{\partial^2 \Psi_{zj}}{\partial \xi^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \Psi_{zj}}{\partial \eta^2} + k_{2j}^2 (ch^2 \xi - \cos^2 \eta) \Psi_{zj} &= 0, \end{aligned} \right\} (3.6)$$

bunda:

$$k_{1j}^2 = \frac{\rho_j \omega^2}{\lambda_j + 2\mu_j} = \frac{\omega^2}{c_{1j}^2 \Gamma_{pj}}; \quad k_{2j}^2 = \frac{\rho_j \omega^2}{\mu_j} = \frac{\omega^2}{c_{2j}^2 \Gamma_{sj}}; \quad J^2 = (ch2\xi - \cos 2\eta) / 2$$

ρ – zichlik; λ, μ – Lamé koefitsiyentlari;

$$\Gamma_{pj} = 1 - \Gamma_{pj}^c(\omega_R) - i\Gamma_{pj}^s(\omega_R), \Gamma_{sj} = 1 - \Gamma_{sj}^c(\omega_R) - i\Gamma_{sj}^s(\omega_R).$$

Elliptik koordinatalarda berilgan Φ_j va Ψ_j yechimni o‘zgaruvchilarni ajratish usuli bilan yechamiz.

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi_j(\xi, \eta, z) &= \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} F_{\phi jk}(\xi) G_{\phi jk}(\eta) Z_{\phi jk}(z), \\ \Psi_{rj}(\xi, \eta, z) &= \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} F_{\psi rjk}(\xi) G_{\psi rjk}(\eta) Z_{\psi rjk}(z), \\ \Psi_{\theta j}(\xi, \eta, z) &= \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} F_{\psi \theta jk}(\xi) G_{\psi \theta jk}(\eta) Z_{\psi \theta jk}(z), \\ \Psi_{zj}(\xi, \eta, z) &= \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} F_{\psi zjk}(\xi) G_{\psi zjk}(\eta) Z_{\psi zjk}(z), \end{aligned} \quad (3.7)$$

U holda (3.6) tenglamani bittasini umumiy holda yechilishini ko‘ramiz:

$$\frac{1}{F_{\phi jk}(\xi)} \frac{d^2 F_{\phi jk}(\xi)}{d\xi^2} + k_1^2 ach2\xi = -\frac{1}{G_{\phi jk}(\eta)} \frac{d^2 G_{\phi jk}(\eta)}{d\eta^2} + k_1^2 a \cos 2\eta, \quad (3.8)$$

Bu ifodani ixtiyoriy A o‘zgarmas songa tenglashtirsak, u holda quyidagini

olamiz:

$$\frac{d^2 F_{\phi jk}(\xi)}{d\xi^2} + (b - 0.5a^2(k_1^2 - \gamma^2)ch2\xi) F_{\phi jk}(\xi) = 0, \quad (3.9)$$

$$\frac{d^2 G_{\phi jk}(\eta)}{d\eta^2} - (b - 0.5a^2(k_1^2 - \gamma^2)\cos 2\eta) G_{\phi jk}(\eta) = 0, \quad (3.10)$$

$$\frac{d^2 Z_{\psi jk}(z)}{dz^2} + \gamma^2 Z_{\psi jk}(z) = 0.$$

Agar $G(\eta)$ (3.10) ni umumiy yechimi bo‘lsa, u holda quyidagi munosabat o‘rinli bo‘ladi:

$$G(i\xi) = F(\xi) \quad (3.11)$$

Endi (3.10) tenglamani yechimi $F(\xi)$ bo‘lsa, u holda quyidagi o‘rinli bo‘ladi:

$$G(\eta) = F\left(-\frac{\eta}{i}\right), \quad (3.12)$$

Shuning uchun bu tenglamalarni alohida o‘rganish talab yetilmaydi. Yuqorida keltirilgan (3.12) tenglamani to‘liq o‘rganamiz

$$\frac{d^2 G(\eta)}{d\eta^2} + (a + 16q_1 \cos 2\eta)G(\eta) = 0, \quad (3.13)$$

$$a = -A - \frac{k_1^2}{2}; q_1 = -\frac{k_1^2}{32}$$

bu yerda:

Shunday qilib chegaraviy shartlarni qanoatlantiruvchi (3.8) va (3.9) tenglamalarni yechimlarini topamiz.

Oxirgi (2.19) tenglamani yechimini qator ko‘rinishida izlaymiz:

$$G(\eta) = g_0(\eta) + \varepsilon g_1(\eta) + \varepsilon^2 g_2(\eta) + \dots = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \varepsilon^k g_k(\eta) \quad (3.14)$$

Yechimni (3.13) tenglamaga qo‘yib oldidagi koeffitsiyentlarni nolga tenglashtirsak, u holda quyidagi

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{g}_0(\eta) + \delta g_0(\eta) &= 0 \\ \dot{g}_1(\eta) + \delta g_1(\eta) &= -2g_0 \cos 2\eta \\ \dot{g}_2(\eta) + \delta g_2(\eta) &= -2g_1 \cos 2\eta \end{aligned}$$

ko‘rinishdagi tenglamalar sistemasini olamiz:

$$\dots\dots\dots (3.15)$$

Tahlil va xulosalar.

Bu (3.15) tenglamani yechimini quyidagicha yozish mumkin:

$$u_0 = a \cos(\omega\eta + \beta), \delta = \omega^2,$$

Bunda α va β -ixtiyoriy o‘zgarmas kattaliklar. Xuddi shunday (3.15) ni ikkinchi tenglamasi:

$$\dot{g}_1(\eta) + \omega^2 g_1(\eta) = -2a \cos(\omega\eta + \beta) \cos 2\eta, \quad (3.16)$$

yoki $\dot{g}_1(\eta) + \omega^2 g_1(\eta) = -a \cos[(\omega + 2)\eta + \beta] - a \cos[(\omega - 2)\eta + \beta].$

Bu tenglamani yechimi quyidagicha bo‘ladi:

$$u_1 = \frac{a \cos[(\omega + 2)\eta + \beta]}{4(1 + \omega)} + \frac{a \cos[(\omega - 2)\eta + \beta]}{4(1 - \omega)}.$$

Qolgan yechimlar ham shunday topilib, umumiy holda Mate funksiyasi orqali ifoda qilinadi. Bu yerda a va ω kompleks kattalik hisoblanadi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar

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